

RehabMove 2018: EFFECTS OF SEAT HEIGHT, WHEELCHAIR MASS AND GLOVE USE ON MOBILITY PERFORMANCE IN WHEELCHAIR BASKETBALL

M.J.M. Hoozemans¹, A.M.H. de Witte², R.M.A. van der Slikke², H.E.J. Veeger³, L.H.V. van der Woude⁴, M.A.M. Berger²

¹Faculty of Behavioural and Movement Sciences, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, AMSTERDAM, Netherlands

²The Hague University of Applied Sciences, THE HAGUE, Netherlands

³Department of Biomechanical Engineering, Delft University of Technology, DELFT, Netherlands

⁴Centre for Human Movement Sciences, University Medical Centre Groningen, GRONINGEN, Netherlands

PURPOSE: The aim of this study was to examine the effects of seat height, wheelchair mass and glove use on wheelchair mobility performance (WMP) in elite wheelchair basketball players, while performing a standardized field-based WMP test, and to determine whether these effects are different for wheelchair basketball players of either low or high classification.

METHODS: Elite wheelchair basketball players with a low (n=11, class 1 or 1.5) or high (n=10, class 4 or 4.5) classification performed a standardized field-based WMP test. Players performed the test six times in their own wheelchair, of which five times with different (wheelchair) configurations, i.e. with a higher or lower seat height, with additional distally or centrally located mass, and with use of gloves. The effects of these configurations on performance times on the WMP test and the interaction with classification were determined.

RESULTS: Total performance time on the WMP test was significantly reduced when using a 7.5% lower seat height. Additional mass (7.5%) and glove use did not lead to changes in performance time. High and low classification players showed similar responses to the interventions.

CONCLUSIONS: The presented methodology can be used in a wheelchair fitting process to search for the optimal individual seat height to enhance WMP. Further research should focus on other potentially effective adjustments to wheelchair configurations to optimize WMP in wheelchair basketball.